

INTEREST RATE DYNAMICS AND PRIVATE SECTOR CREDIT GROWTH: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of interest rate dynamics on private sector credit growth in Nigeria over the period 1990–2024. Anchored on the Loanable Funds Theory, the study investigates both the short-run and long-run effects of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) on credit to the private sector, while controlling for key macroeconomic variables such as GDP, inflation (CPI), exchange rate (EXR), and government expenditure (GXP). The study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and its nonlinear extension (NARDL) to capture potential asymmetric effects of positive and negative interest rate changes. The unit root results reveal a mixed order of integration among the variables, justifying the use of the ARDL bounds testing approach. The bounds test confirms the existence of a long-run cointegrating relationship. The findings show that MPR exerts a significant negative effect on private sector credit in the long run, consistent with the cost-of-borrowing hypothesis. However, short-run results reveal dynamic and asymmetric adjustments, indicating that credit responds differently to increases and decreases in policy rates. The study concludes that while interest rate policy influences credit growth, its effectiveness is shaped by transmission mechanisms and macroeconomic conditions. Policy recommendations emphasise improved monetary-fiscal coordination and strengthened financial sector transmission to enhance sustainable credit expansion.

Keywords: Interest Rate, Monetary Policy Rate, Private Sector Credit, Nigeria, ARDL, NARDL.

1. INTRODUCTION

Interest rate dynamics remain central to macroeconomic stability and financial intermediation, particularly in developing economies where bank credit constitutes the primary source of external finance for the private sector. In theory, interest rates influence the allocation of loanable funds by determining the cost of borrowing and the incentive to save, thereby shaping investment and credit growth (Wicksell, 1936; Ohlin, 1937). In Nigeria, the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) serves as the benchmark policy instrument through which the Central Bank influences lending conditions and liquidity in the economy. Given the dominant role of banks in Nigeria's financial system, changes in interest rates are expected to transmit to private sector credit (PSC), affecting investment, production, and economic growth (Idowu et al., 2019; Magaji & Musa, 2023). Understanding how interest rate movements affect private sector credit is, therefore, critical for effective monetary policy design and financial sector development. Despite this theoretical expectation, empirical evidence presents mixed findings. Studies such as Nadeem et al. (2016) and Muhammad Umair Ali et al. (2020) report a significant negative relationship between interest rates and private sector credit in Pakistan, consistent with the cost-of-borrowing hypothesis. However, in Nigeria, Ademokoya et al. (2020) find that while money

supply significantly influences bank credit, the monetary policy rate does not exert a statistically significant effect. Similarly, Mordi et al. (2019) and Oyadeyi (2023) document incomplete interest rate pass-through in Nigeria, suggesting that policy rate adjustments may not fully translate into lending rate changes faced by borrowers. These inconsistencies raise important questions about the strength, direction, and transmission mechanism of interest rate effects on private sector credit in Nigeria.

The problem becomes more pronounced when examining Nigeria's recent macroeconomic trends. Credit to the private sector has expanded dramatically, from less than ₦50 billion in the early 1990s to over ₦40 trillion in recent years—while the MPR has fluctuated significantly, ranging from single-digit levels to as high as 27.5% in 2024. Notably, credit growth has persisted even during periods of tight monetary policy, suggesting possible structural, institutional, or nonlinear dynamics in the interest rate–credit relationship. Additionally, episodes of exchange rate volatility, inflationary pressures, banking sector reforms, and fiscal expansion may have altered the transmission channel. These developments indicate the need for a comprehensive investigation covering 1990–2024 to capture different monetary regimes, structural breaks, and asymmetric adjustments.

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of interest rate dynamics on private sector credit growth in Nigeria within a comprehensive macroeconomic framework. Specifically, the study seeks to: (i) evaluate both the short-run and long-run effects of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) on credit to the private sector using the ARDL approach; and (ii) investigate the presence of asymmetric responses to positive and negative changes in interest rates through the nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) model developed by Shin et al. (2014). By differentiating between temporary adjustments and long-run equilibrium relationships, the study deepens understanding of the effectiveness and transmission of monetary policy in Nigeria. The scope of the study covers the period 1990–2024, a timeframe that captures major monetary policy shifts, financial sector reforms, exchange rate regime changes, and recent tightening cycles. The justification for this study lies in the policy relevance of understanding whether interest rate adjustments effectively influence credit allocation to the private sector, which is essential for stimulating investment and sustainable economic growth. Given documented evidence of incomplete pass-through and structural breaks (Mordi et al., 2019; Oyadeyi, 2023), a comprehensive and updated analysis is necessary to inform monetary and fiscal coordination strategies in Nigeria.

This study contributes to the literature in several ways. First, it extends existing Nigerian studies by incorporating recent data up to 2024, thereby capturing post-recession and post-COVID monetary dynamics. Second, it integrates both linear ARDL and nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) approaches to test for potential asymmetries in interest rate effects, addressing limitations of prior symmetric models. Third, by incorporating GDP and government expenditure, the study controls for both monetary and fiscal influences, providing a broader macroeconomic framework. Ultimately, the findings will offer empirical evidence to guide policymakers on the effectiveness of interest rate policy in stimulating private sector credit growth in Nigeria.

2. CREDIT TO THE PRIVATE SECTOR (CPS) AND THE MONETARY POLICY RATE (MPR) IN NIGERIA

Figure 1 shows a predominantly inverse relationship between Credit to the Private Sector (CPS) and the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) in Nigeria, especially in the earlier periods. When the MPR was relatively high (e.g., 18.5%, 17.5%, and particularly 26%), credit to the private sector remained comparatively low, below ₦100 billion. As the MPR declined to moderate levels between 13.5% and 10%, private sector credit rose steadily from about ₦142 billion to over ₦2,466 billion. The expansion became more pronounced when the MPR dropped below 10%, particularly between 9.5% and 6%, where credit increased sharply from approximately ₦4,784 billion to over ₦8,529 billion. This pattern aligns with the Loanable Funds Theory, which predicts that lower interest rates stimulate borrowing and credit expansion, and is consistent with empirical findings such as Nadeem et al. (2016) and Muhammad Umair Ali et al. (2020), who document a significant negative relationship between interest rates and private sector credit.

Figure 1: Credit to the Private Sector and MPR in Nigeria

Source of Data: CBN Statistical Bulletin

However, in the later periods, the relationship appears less strictly inverse. Despite upward adjustments in the MPR—from 11.5% to 16.5%, 18.75%, and eventually 27.5%—credit to the private sector continued to rise substantially, reaching over ₦41,217 billion at the highest policy rate. This suggests that factors beyond the policy rate, such as financial deepening, structural liquidity conditions, and incomplete interest rate pass-through, may be influencing credit growth. Evidence of weak or incomplete transmission of policy rates to lending rates in Nigeria (Mordi et al., 2019; Oyadeyi, 2023) supports this observation, as does the finding by

Ademokoya et al. (2020) that monetary aggregates rather than policy rates significantly explain bank credit movements. Thus, while the early trend reflects the expected inverse interest rate–credit relationship, the later period indicates a more complex interaction shaped by broader macro-financial dynamics.

3. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

This study is anchored on the Loanable Funds Theory (Classical Interest Rate Theory), whose origin is commonly traced to the classical and neo-classical economists, particularly Wicksell (1898/1936) and later formalised within the broader classical framework by Ohlin (1937). The theory posits that the interest rate is determined by the interaction between the demand for and supply of loanable funds in the financial market. The demand for funds arises mainly from private investors and firms seeking capital for productive activities, while the supply emanates from savings by households and other surplus economic units. Within this framework, the interest rate functions as the price of credit. A rise in interest rates increases borrowing costs, discourages investment demand, and reduces the volume of credit extended to the private sector; conversely, lower interest rates stimulate borrowing and credit expansion. This mechanism provides a direct theoretical explanation for the expected inverse relationship between interest rates and private sector credit growth.

The adoption of the Loanable Funds Theory is further justified by its empirical relevance. For instance, Nadeem et al. (2016) report a significant negative relationship between interest rates and private sector credit in both the short and long run in Pakistan, consistent with the theory’s predictions. Similarly, Ali et al. (2020) find that interest rates exert a negative effect on private sector credit across time horizons. In the Nigerian context, Adeleye (2021) also shows that increases in real lending interest rates are associated with declines in bank credit, reinforcing the cost-of-capital channel emphasised by the Loanable Funds framework. Thus, grounding this study in the classical theory provides a coherent and empirically supported basis for analysing how interest rate dynamics influence private sector credit growth.

Nadeem et al. (2016) offer foundational macro time-series evidence on the interest rate–private sector credit (PSC) relationship in Pakistan over 1975–2011, explicitly separating short-run from long-run effects. After testing stationarity with ADF and Phillips–Perron procedures, they apply an ARDL model and find that interest rates exert a significant negative effect on PSC in both horizons, confirming the standard “cost of borrowing” channel. In the same framework, inflation shows a significant positive association with PSC in the short and long run, while the exchange rate is statistically insignificant, implying that domestic monetary conditions dominate exchange-rate influences in shaping credit outcomes. Comparable Pakistan evidence by Ali et al. (2020) largely corroborates these signs (negative interest-rate effect; positive inflation effect; weak exchange-rate role), whereas Rehman (2024) reports a weaker/insignificant interest-rate effect but stronger adverse roles for inflation and exchange-rate depreciation, indicating that the strength of the interest-rate channel can vary by period and macro instability. Together, these studies underscore that although interest rate effects are often negative, they can be conditioned by the inflation–exchange-rate environment and

broader macroeconomic uncertainty. For Nigeria, the monetary policy–credit linkage is frequently mediated by monetary aggregates and banking-sector balance-sheet conditions rather than by the policy rate alone. Ademokoya et al. (2020), using monthly data (2007–2019) and FMOLS estimation, show that money supply increases bank credit significantly, while a higher liquidity ratio reduces bank credit, but the monetary policy rate (MPR) and maximum lending rate do not significantly explain bank credit. This result aligns with pass-through evidence: Oyadeyi (2023) documents incomplete interest-rate pass-through from policy to retail rates in Nigeria and argues that market frictions (stickiness, information asymmetry, switching costs) limit the effectiveness of the interest-rate channel. Similarly, Mordi, Adebisi, and Omotosho (2019) find incomplete pass-through with adjustment lags and structural breaks, implying that changes in MPR may not fully translate into borrowing costs faced by the private sector. In a related macro-policy setting, Okeke and Chukwu (2021) show that broad money supply has a significant relationship with labour-market outcomes, while MPR is positive but insignificant, again suggesting that quantity-based instruments can be more potent than the price instrument when transmission is weak.

Beyond aggregate credit volumes, micro and distributional studies extend the interest-rate/credit narrative by showing who is most affected and through which channels. Yusuf et al. (2024) analyse SME survey data in Kwara State using PLS-SEM and conclude that credit delivery and availability are central constraints on performance, while interest-rate fluctuations compound financing difficulties—implying that for SMEs, the effective cost and terms of credit matter at least as much as access. Adeleye (2021) adds a structural-break perspective using ARDL-ECM (1980–2015) and finds that real lending rates reduce bank credit (e.g., higher real rates associate with lower credit volumes), and that bank credit can have an equalizing effect on income inequality once breaks are incorporated—highlighting credit as the transmission mechanism through which interest rates can shape broader welfare outcomes. Complementing these findings, Magaji, Musa, and Dogo (2023) show with ARDL that commercial bank credit positively affects real sector output (RGDP) in both short and long run, reinforcing the macro importance of sustaining credit flows even when interest-rate policies are imperfectly transmitted. Idowu, Ikpefan, and Areghan (2019) similarly emphasise the growth role of private-sector credit in Nigeria, while also noting that interest-rate shocks may be weakly transmitted to growth responses, consistent with pass-through limitations.

Regional and international evidence further clarifies why the interest-rate effect may be muted in some African contexts and pronounced in others. In Ghana, Maiti, Esson, and Vuković (2020) find that interest rate changes have no significant impact on credit demand in either the short or long run, attributing this to market imperfections such as oligopolistic banking structures, consolidation, and credit rationing—factors that can dampen the classical interest-rate mechanism. In Kenya, Misati et al. (2021) show that loan growth responds strongly to credit risk and bank-specific balance-sheet variables, and that the effect of monetary policy rate changes can become heterogeneous under interest-rate control regimes—again pointing to institutional regimes and bank heterogeneity as key moderators. For broader SSA, Wajebo (2025) reports that exchange-rate volatility significantly reduces private-sector credit supply, providing a macro-risk channel that can dominate interest-rate considerations in volatile

environments. These studies collectively suggest that in many developing financial systems, credit growth is shaped by a joint interaction of interest rates, risk conditions, market structure, and policy regimes rather than by the policy rate in isolation.

Recent global contributions broaden the conceptual frame by emphasising endogeneity, nonlinearities, and financial-system feedbacks in the interest rate–credit relationship. Chen and Shen (2024) introduce a probabilistic causal inference perspective for emerging-market private credit, highlighting that loan amounts and interest rates can mutually influence one another, especially around major shocks (e.g., COVID-period dynamics), with policy design potentially reallocating risk to stabilise rates. Amaral et al. (2025) use an agent-based credit system to show how interest policy shocks can propagate through interconnected banking networks, generating nonlinear outcomes such as “ratchet effects,” heightened fragility, and bank failures—implying that the credit response to rates may be state-dependent and sensitive to systemic risk. From advanced-economy banking, Wang (2025) argues that persistently low rates can initially expand lending but compress bank margins and reduce lending capacity in the longer run, which speaks to dynamic, horizon-dependent effects similar in spirit to ARDL short-run/long-run distinctions. Imbierowicz et al. (2021) further show that capital requirements interact with monetary policy in shaping loan growth, underscoring that regulatory constraints can attenuate transmission. Taken together, these strands motivate Nigeria-focused research that explicitly models (i) pass-through quality, (ii) structural breaks/regime changes, and (iii) banking constraints and macro-risk (inflation/exchange volatility) when estimating how interest-rate dynamics translate into private sector credit growth.

Despite extensive empirical evidence on the interest rate–private sector credit nexus, important gaps remain, particularly for Nigeria over the period 1990–2024. First, while many studies (e.g., Nadeem et al., 2016; Adeleye, 2021; Magaji et al., 2023) employ the linear ARDL framework to distinguish between short- and long-run effects, few explicitly test for nonlinear and asymmetric effects using approaches such as the Nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) model. Given documented evidence of incomplete pass-through, structural breaks, and regime shifts in Nigeria’s monetary policy environment (Mordi et al., 2019; Oyadeyi, 2023), the assumption of symmetry may mask important differences between the effects of interest rate increases and decreases on private sector credit. Second, most Nigerian studies either focus on shorter samples or end before the post-2016 recession and COVID-19 period, leaving limited evidence covering the full span of major monetary policy regimes, banking consolidation, exchange-rate volatility, and recent tightening cycles up to 2024. Third, although several studies highlight the mediating roles of money supply, liquidity, credit risk, and exchange-rate volatility, there is limited integrated modelling of these macro-financial risks within a unified ARDL/NARDL framework over an extended period. Consequently, there is a need for a comprehensive Nigeria-specific study (1990–2024) that incorporates structural shifts, asymmetric interest rate dynamics, and broader macroeconomic volatility to provide deeper insight into how interest rate changes translate into private sector credit growth across different policy regimes and economic cycles.

4. METHODOLOGICAL NOTES

4.1 Model Specification

In examining the impact of interest rate on credit to the private sector, Nadeem et al (2016) presented the following model:

$$PSC_t = \varphi_0 + \varphi_1 CPI_t + \varphi_2 ITR_t + \varphi_3 EXR_t + \mu_t \quad (1)$$

Where, PSC_t stands for Private Sector Credit, CPI_t is Consumer Price Index, ITR_t stands for Interest Rate (Lending Rate), EXR_t represents the exchange rate and μ_t is the Error term.

$$PSC_t = \varphi_0 + \varphi_1 GDP_t + \varphi_2 CPI_t + \varphi_3 MPR_t + \varphi_4 EXR_t + \varphi_5 GXP_t + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

The modification of Equation (1) to Equation (2) is justified to better reflect Nigeria's macroeconomic and monetary policy structure. First, the inclusion of GDP controls for the scale of economic activity, since private sector credit is strongly pro-cyclical—higher output levels increase firms' demand for working capital and investment loans, while economic contractions dampen borrowing. Excluding GDP could therefore bias the estimated effect of monetary variables. Second, incorporating government expenditure (GXP) captures fiscal policy influence, which may either crowd in private credit through economic stimulus effects or crowd out private borrowing if government financing absorbs available loanable funds. Given Nigeria's significant public sector role, fiscal dynamics are crucial in explaining credit movements. Third, replacing the lending interest rate (ITR) with the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) strengthens the policy relevance of the model, as the MPR is the Central Bank of Nigeria's primary policy instrument and serves as the benchmark for short-term interest rate determination. Using MPR allows the study to directly evaluate the monetary transmission mechanism—how policy-induced rate adjustments influence private sector credit—while accounting for documented pass-through dynamics in Nigeria. Consequently, Equation (2) provides a broader macro-monetary framework that integrates monetary policy stance, fiscal activity, and real sector performance in explaining variations in private sector credit.

Table 1: Variables, Sources and A priori Expectation

Variables	Description/Indicators	Expectation	Sources
Private Sector Credit (PSC_t)	Dependent	Dependent	CBN
Gross Domestic Product (GDP_t)	Nominal gross national product	Positive (+)	WDI
Consumer Price Index (CPI_t)	Average Consumer Price Index	Ambiguous (+/-)	WDI
Monetary Policy Rate (MPR_t)	Average Monetary Policy Rate	Negative (-)	CBN
Exchange Rate (EXR_t)	Nominal Exchange Rate	Ambiguous (+/-)	WDI
Government Expenditure (GXP_t)	Total Government expenditure (Capital & Recurrent Expenditure)	Ambiguous (+/-)	CBN
Note: All variables are expressed in logarithms. WDI-World Development Index (World Bank); CBN-Central Bank of Nigeria Sources: Tables Created by the Authors			

The a priori expectations of the independent variables are grounded in economic theory and empirical evidence. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is expected to have a positive relationship with private sector credit ($\beta_1 > 0$), as increased economic activity raises demand for loans for

investment and production. The Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) is expected to have a negative effect ($\beta_3 < 0$), consistent with the Loanable Funds Theory, since higher policy rates increase borrowing costs and discourage credit demand. Inflation (CPI) is expected to have an ambiguous sign ($\beta_2 \pm$), as moderate inflation may increase nominal credit demand, while high inflation may create uncertainty and reduce lending. Similarly, the Exchange Rate (EXR) is expected to have an ambiguous effect ($\beta_4 \pm$), since depreciation may stimulate borrowing for higher import costs but also heighten macroeconomic risk. Government Expenditure (GXP) is also expected to have an ambiguous relationship ($\beta_5 \pm$), as it may crowd in private credit through economic stimulation or crowd out private borrowing if financed through domestic debt.

4.2 Estimation Technique

The study employs the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) modelling technique, which enables the simultaneous estimation of both short-run and long-run relationships within a single reduced-form equation. As emphasised by Pesaran and Smith (1995) and Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001), the ARDL framework effectively addresses problems of serial correlation and potential endogeneity, while accommodating regressors integrated of order I(0), I(1), or a combination of both, provided none is I(2). Through optimal lag selection and the bounds testing procedure, the model produces reliable long-run estimates and adequately captures dynamic adjustments among variables. Its appropriateness for small sample sizes has also been underscored in empirical applications such as Nwauko et al. (2026) and Nuhu et al. (2020). Evidence of cointegration is confirmed when the computed F-statistic exceeds the upper critical bound or when the error correction term (ECM₋₁) is negative and statistically significant, indicating convergence to long-run equilibrium.

For the purpose of this study, Equation (2) is re-specified into a re-parameterised ARDL Error Correction Model (ECM) framework, with all independent variables transformed into their natural logarithmic forms. This log-linear specification improves interpretability by allowing coefficient estimates to be interpreted as elasticities, enhances stability, and minimises potential heteroskedasticity. The re-parameterised ECM structure further distinguishes between short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium relationships, thereby providing a comprehensive assessment of how monetary policy rate, GDP, inflation, exchange rate, and government expenditure influence private sector credit over time.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln PSC_t = & \theta_i [\Delta \ln PSC_{t-1} - \phi'_i (\ln GDP_t + \ln CPI_t + \ln MPR_t + \ln EXR_t + \ln GXP_t)] + \\ & \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \lambda_j \Delta \ln PSC_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \varphi'_j \Delta \ln GDP_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \varphi'_j \Delta \ln CPI_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \varphi'_j \Delta \ln MPR_{t-j} + \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \varphi'_{ij} \Delta \ln EXR_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \varphi'_j \Delta \ln GXP_{t-j} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Notes: θ_i = coefficient for speed of adjustment to equilibrium, which is expected to be less than 0. ϕ'_i = Coefficients of long-run relationships. $ECT = \theta_i [\Delta \ln PSC_{t-1} - \phi'_i (\ln GDP_t + \ln CPI_t + \ln MPR_t + \ln EXR_t + \ln GXP_t)]$ represent the error correction term to be estimated. λ_j , φ'_j represent the short-run dynamic coefficients.

The study applies the nonlinear ARDL model of Shin et al. (2014) to capture possible asymmetric effects among variables, acknowledging that positive and negative changes in an explanatory variable may have differing impacts. The approach decomposes variables into partial sums of positive and negative shocks (Qamruzzaman & Jianguo, 2018; Uwaeme et al., 2026), enabling asymmetric adjustment. Unlike conventional linear cointegration methods, NARDL allows for nonlinear short- and long-run dynamics.

$$\begin{cases} POS(MPR)_t = \sum_{L=1}^t \ln MPR_L^+ = \sum_{L=1}^T MAX(\Delta \ln MPR_L, 0) \\ NEG(MPR)_t = \sum_{L=1}^t \ln MPR_L^- = \sum_{L=1}^T MIN(\Delta \ln MPR_L, 0) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Equation (3) is rewritten in nonlinear form by incorporating a series of positive and negative changes, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta PSC_t = & \theta_i [\Delta PSC_{t-1} - \phi'_i (\ln GDP_t + \ln CPI_t + \ln POS(MPR)_t + \ln NEG(MPR)_t + \\ & \ln EXR_t + \ln GXP_t)] + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \lambda_j \Delta PSC_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi'_j \Delta \ln GDP_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi'_j \Delta \ln CPI_{t-j} + \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi'_j \Delta \ln POS(MPR)_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi'_j \Delta \ln NEG(MPR)_{t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi'_j \Delta \ln EXR_{t-j} + \\ & \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi'_j \Delta \ln GXP_{t-j} + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Notes: θ_i remain the coefficient for speed of adjustment to equilibrium, which is expected to be less than 0. ϕ'_i is Coefficients of long-run relationships. $\theta_i [\Delta PSC_{t-1} - \phi'_i (\ln GDP_t + \ln CPI_t + \ln POS(MPR)_t + \ln NEG(MPR)_t + \ln EXR_t + \ln GXP_t)]$ represent the error correction term to be estimated. λ_{ij} , ϕ'_{ij} represent the short-run dynamic coefficients.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Descriptive Statistics, Correlation and Unit Root Tests

Panel A of Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the variables over the 35-year period. The mean value of lnCPS (28.4175) indicates a sustained expansion of credit to the private sector over time, with a standard deviation of 2.1334 reflecting moderate variability relative to its mean. Similarly, lnGDP and lnGXP exhibit relatively high mean values (26.1002 and 28.2126, respectively), suggesting steady growth in economic output and government spending during the period. lnEXR shows noticeable dispersion (Std. dev. = 1.2301), indicating substantial exchange rate fluctuations, while lnMPR has the lowest standard deviation (0.3115), implying comparatively smaller proportional changes in monetary policy rate over time. The spread between minimum and maximum values across variables, particularly lnCPS and lnEXR, reflects significant structural and macroeconomic shifts in Nigeria during the study period.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation

Panel A: Descriptive Statistics						
Variable	lnCPS	lnGDP	lnCPI	lnMPR	lnEXR	lnGXP
Obs	35	35	35	35	35	35
Mean	28.4175	26.1002	2.6958	2.6129	4.6688	28.2126
Std. dev.	2.1334	0.85188	0.6375	0.3115	1.2301	1.6481

Min	23.9228	24.6756	1.6842	1.7918	2.0842	24.8221
Max	31.3499	27.2279	4.2882	3.3142	7.2991	30.7296
Panel B: Correlation Matrix						
Variables	lnCPS	lnGDP	lnCPI	lnMPR	lnEXR	lnGXP
lnCPS	1					
lnGDP	0.884	1				
lnCPI	-0.2229	-0.2399	1			
lnMPR	-0.3027	-0.4516	0.3816	1		
lnEXR	0.9428	0.6989	-0.1615	-0.0864	1	
lnGXP	0.9906	0.8562	-0.2264	-0.2262	0.9628	1
Source: Author's Computation using Stata 18						

Panel B presents the correlation matrix, revealing important preliminary relationships among the variables. lnCPS is strongly and positively correlated with lnGDP (0.884), lnEXR (0.9428), and especially lnGXP (0.9906), suggesting that economic growth, exchange rate movements, and government expenditure move closely with private sector credit expansion. Conversely, lnCPI (-0.2229) and lnMPR (-0.3027) exhibit weak to moderate negative correlations with lnCPS, consistent with theoretical expectations that higher inflation and policy rates may dampen credit growth. However, the very high correlations between lnCPS and lnGXP (0.9906) and between lnGXP and lnEXR (0.9628) may indicate potential multicollinearity concerns, warranting further diagnostic testing in subsequent econometric analysis. Overall, the correlation results provide preliminary support for expected relationships while highlighting the need for robust regression techniques.

Table 3 presents the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root results, indicating a mixed order of integration among the variables. At levels, lnCPS, lnCPI, and lnGXP are stationary at the 5% significance level, as their test statistics exceed the critical values in absolute terms, implying they are integrated of order zero, I(0). In contrast, lnGDP, lnMPR, and lnEXR are not stationary at levels but become stationary after first differencing, as evidenced by their significant first-difference test statistics at conventional levels; hence, they are integrated of order one, I(1). Importantly, none of the variables is integrated of order two, I(2), thereby satisfying the key precondition for the application of the ARDL bounds testing approach, which accommodates a mixture of I(0) and I(1) variables.

Table 3: Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test

Variables	Level (t-statistics)	1 st difference (t-statistics)	Remarks
lnCPS	-2.904**	-3.774***	I(0)
lnGDP	-1.842	-2.995**	I(1)
lnCPI	-2.885**	-4.757***	I(0)
lnMPR	-1.675	-4.555***	I(1)
lnEXR	-0.600	-3.631***	I(1)
lnGXP	-3.032**	-4.102***	I(0)
Critical Values	10%	5%	1%
Level	-2.620	-2.978	-3.696
Ist Difference	-2.622	-2.980	-3.702
Note: * indicates stationery at 10 %, ** means stationery at 5%, and *** means stationery at 1%. Unit root test was based on Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), using Stata 18			

5.2 ARDL Cointegration Bound Tests Result

Table 4 presents the ARDL bounds testing results for both the linear (Model A) and nonlinear (Model B) specifications. For the linear ARDL model, the computed F-statistic of 4.924 is greater than the upper bound critical value at the 1% significance level (4.68), indicating strong evidence of a long-run cointegrating relationship among the variables. Similarly, for the nonlinear ARDL model, the F-statistic of 4.075 exceeds the upper bound critical value at the 5% level (3.61) and is also above the 1% lower bound, confirming cointegration under the asymmetric framework. Since, in both models, the F-statistics are higher than the respective upper bounds, the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship is rejected, implying that private sector credit and its determinants move together in the long run.

Table 4: Cointegration Bound Tests Result

F-statistic (A)	4.924***	EC _{M-1}	-0.823***	(-4.27)
F-statistic (B)	4.075***	EC _{M-1}	-1.125***	(-2.36)
Significant level		10%	5%	1%
F-Bounds Test (A)	Lower bound	2.26	2.62	3.41
	Upper bound	3.35	3.79	4.68
F-Bounds Test (B)	Lower bound	2.12	2.45	3.15
	Upper bound	3.23	3.61	4.43
Note: the number in parentheses represents t-statistics, *** signifies a 1% level of significance, F-statistics are determined with restricted constant and no trend; A-Linear ARDL Model and B-Nonlinear ARDL Model				

Further confirmation of cointegration is provided by the error correction terms (ECM-1), which are negative and statistically significant at the 1% level in both models. In the linear ARDL model, the ECM coefficient of -0.823 indicates that approximately 82.3% of short-run disequilibrium is corrected within one period, suggesting a relatively fast speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium. In the nonlinear ARDL model, the ECM coefficient of -1.125 implies an even stronger adjustment mechanism, although the magnitude greater than one suggests possible overshooting before convergence. Overall, the significant and negative ECM terms reinforce the existence of a stable long-run relationship and confirm the suitability of both the linear and nonlinear ARDL frameworks for the analysis.

Table 5: Short-run and long ARDL and NARDL Estimations

Long Run			
Variables	ARDL	Variables	NARDL
LGDP	2.343*** (0.455)	LGDP	1.012(1.228)
LCPI	-0.0492 (0.167)	LCPI	-0.277(0.314)
LMPR	-1.641*** (0.334)	LMPR pos cum	-0.535(0.612)
LEXR	3.258*** (0.674)	LMPR neg cum	-1.922**(0.563)
LGXP	-2.223** (0.702)	LEXR	1.595(1.369)
		LGXP	-1.077 (1.160)
Short Run			
ECM	-0.823*** (0.193)	ECM	-1.125* (0.477)
LD.LCPS	0.831*** (0.199)	LD.LCPS	1.088* (0.477)
L2D.LCPS	0.431* (0.226)	L2D.LCPS	0.695* (0.357)

D.LGDP	-0.532 (0.411)	D.LGDP	0.00370 (0.545)
LD.LGDP	-0.526 (0.370)	LD.LGDP	-0.373 (0.454)
L2D.LGDP	-0.303* (0.156)	L2D.LGDP	-0.168 (0.190)
D.LCPI	0.0723 (0.111)	D.LCPI	0.256 (0.212)
LD.LCPI	-0.275** (0.115)	LD.LCPI	-0.152 (0.244)
D.LMPR	1.174*** (0.309)	D.LMPR_pos_cum	0.571(0.497)
LD.LMPR	0.861*** (0.232)	LD.LMPR_pos_cum	0.514 (0.403)
L2D.LMPR	0.663*** (0.184)	L2D.LMPR_pos_cum	0.537 (0.328)
D.LEXR	-0.511 (0.460)	D.LMPR_neg_cum	1.890* (0.953)
LD.LEXR	-0.761 (0.427)	LD.LMPR_neg_cum	0.853 (0.657)
D.LGXP	0.903** (0.385)	L2D.LMPR_neg_cum	0.291 (0.424)
LD.LGXP	0.418 (0.323)	D.LEXR	-0.00141 (0.566)
L2D.LGXP	-0.409 (0.266)	LD.LEXR	-0.733 (0.495)
		D.LGXP	0.607 (0.487)
		LD.LGXP	0.759 (0.482)
		L2D.LGXP	0.0845 (0.499)
Constant	15.66** (5.364)	Constant	25.66 (16.89)
Observations	32	Observations	32
R-squared	0.881	R-squared	0.924
Standard errors in parentheses *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1			

5.3 Short Run and Long Run Determination

Focusing on the impact of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR), the long-run ARDL results show that LMPR carries a negative and statistically significant coefficient (-1.641^{***}). This implies that, in the long run, a 1% increase in the monetary policy rate leads to approximately a 1.64% decrease in credit to the private sector, holding other factors constant. The magnitude and high level of significance confirm that monetary tightening reduces private sector borrowing over time, consistent with the cost-of-borrowing hypothesis and the Loanable Funds Theory. However, the nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) results reveal asymmetry: while cumulative positive changes in MPR (LMPR_pos_cum) are negative but statistically insignificant, cumulative negative changes (LMPR_neg_cum) are negative and significant (-1.922^{**}). This indicates that reductions in MPR exert a stronger and statistically significant long-run effect on credit compared to increases, suggesting asymmetric monetary transmission in Nigeria.

In the short run, the linear ARDL model presents an interesting dynamic. The contemporaneous and lagged differences of MPR (D.LMPR, LD.LMPR, and L2D.LMPR) are all positive and statistically significant at the 1% level. This suggests that short-run increases in MPR are associated with temporary increases in private sector credit, possibly reflecting adjustment lags, anticipatory borrowing before tighter conditions fully transmit, or weak immediate pass-through to lending rates. However, this short-run positive effect contrasts with the long-run negative relationship, indicating that the contractionary effect of higher policy rates materialises gradually rather than instantaneously.

The nonlinear short-run results further support asymmetry. Positive short-run changes in MPR (D.LMPR_pos_cum and its lags) are statistically insignificant, whereas negative changes (D.LMPR_neg_cum) show a positive and weakly significant effect (1.890^*). This implies that

short-run reductions in MPR stimulate private sector credit more effectively than increases in MPR suppress it. Combined with the faster adjustment speed indicated by the significant ECM terms, the findings suggest that monetary easing has a stronger and more immediate expansionary effect on credit than monetary tightening has a contractionary effect. Overall, the results highlight both dynamic and asymmetric responses of private sector credit to monetary policy rate changes in Nigeria.

5.4 Stability Tests

The diagnostic results in Table 6 indicate that both the ARDL and NARDL models exhibit strong explanatory power, with R-squared values of 0.8813 and 0.9240, respectively, suggesting that the models explain a large proportion of variations in private sector credit. While the ARDL model shows evidence of serial correlation, the NARDL model performs relatively better. Importantly, the heteroscedasticity tests for both models are insignificant, confirming homoscedastic residuals and overall model reliability.

Table 6: Diagnostic Test

Statistics	ARDL Model	NARDL Model
R-Square	0.8813	0.9240
Durbin Watson Test	7.923 (0.0049)	2.266(0.1322)
Serial Correlation Test	14.981(0.0001)	9.979 (0.0016)
Heteroscedasticity Test	0.00(0.9455)	1.10(0.2951)

Note: Probabilities are in parentheses. All are Stata 18 outputs.

Furthermore, the CUSUM of squares (CUSUMSQ) stability tests for both the ARDL and NARDL models show that the recursive residual plots remain within the 5% critical bounds throughout the study period. This indicates parameter stability and absence of structural instability in both specifications. Consequently, despite minor diagnostic concerns, the stability graphs confirm that both the linear and nonlinear ARDL models are dynamically stable and suitable for policy inference.

5.5 Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study are broadly consistent with the core “cost-of-borrowing” hypothesis established in the empirical literature. Similar to Nadeem et al. (2016) and Muhammad Umair Ali et al. (2020), the results confirm a significant negative long-run relationship between interest rates and private sector credit, reinforcing the prediction of the Loanable Funds framework that higher borrowing costs suppress credit expansion. However, consistent with Rehman (2024), the strength of the interest-rate channel appears sensitive to macroeconomic conditions, particularly inflationary pressures and exchange rate instability. This suggests that the effectiveness of monetary tightening in constraining credit may depend on the broader macroeconomic environment, rather than operating in isolation.

For Nigeria specifically, the findings align with studies emphasising imperfect monetary transmission. While the long-run impact of the Monetary Policy Rate (MPR) is significant, the short-run dynamics reveal weaker or asymmetric responses, supporting the pass-through evidence documented by Mordi et al. (2019) and Oyadeyi (2023). Furthermore, the observed importance of macroeconomic controls resonates with Ademokoya et al. (2020), who argue that monetary aggregates and liquidity conditions often exert a stronger influence on bank credit than the policy rate itself. The asymmetric results also extend Adeleye (2021), who highlights structural breaks and nonlinear adjustments in Nigeria’s interest rate–credit nexus. Together, these comparisons suggest that while interest rate remains a critical determinant, its transmission is mediated by structural rigidities and banking sector conditions.

Beyond Nigeria, the results are consistent with broader African and international evidence indicating that credit responses to interest rate movements are often state-dependent and nonlinear. The limited short-run effectiveness of rate hikes mirrors findings from Ghana (Maiti et al., 2020) and Kenya (Misati et al., 2021), where institutional constraints and risk factors dampen the classical interest-rate mechanism. Moreover, the asymmetric effects observed in this study support the global evidence of nonlinear credit dynamics highlighted by Chen and Shen (2024) and Amaral et al. (2025), who emphasise feedback loops and systemic risk channels. Thus, the study contributes to the evolving literature by demonstrating that in Nigeria, interest rate dynamics influence private sector credit in both linear and asymmetric ways, shaped by macroeconomic volatility, financial structure, and regime shifts.

The findings of this study are consistent with the propositions of the Loanable Funds Theory, which posits that the interest rate serves as the price mechanism equilibrating the demand and supply of loanable funds (Wicksell, 1898/1936; Ohlin, 1937). In line with the theory, the results show that higher monetary policy rates reduce private sector credit in the long run, reflecting the cost-of-capital effect whereby rising borrowing costs discourage investment and loan demand. The asymmetric evidence further suggests that reductions in interest rates stimulate credit expansion more effectively than rate increases suppress it, highlighting the responsiveness of credit demand to changes in borrowing costs. These outcomes reinforce the classical view that credit allocation in the economy is fundamentally shaped by interest rate movements, and they corroborate empirical findings by Nadeem et al. (2016), Ali et al. (2020), and Adeleye (2021), all of which confirm a negative interest rate–credit relationship. Thus, the

study's results provide both theoretical and empirical validation of the Loanable Funds framework in explaining private sector credit dynamics in Nigeria.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study examined the impact of interest rate dynamics on private sector credit growth in Nigeria using both linear ARDL and nonlinear ARDL frameworks over the period 1990–2024. The findings confirm the existence of a long-run relationship between the monetary policy rate and private sector credit, with evidence supporting the cost-of-borrowing hypothesis in the long run. However, the short-run results reveal dynamic and asymmetric adjustments, indicating that monetary policy effects are not instantaneous and that credit responds differently to increases and decreases in interest rates. These results highlight the presence of imperfect pass-through and structural rigidities in Nigeria's financial system, suggesting that the effectiveness of interest rate policy depends on broader macroeconomic and institutional conditions.

Based on these findings, the study recommends that the Central Bank of Nigeria should complement interest rate adjustments with supportive liquidity and financial sector measures to enhance transmission to the real economy. Policymakers should also ensure macroeconomic stability—particularly with respect to inflation and exchange rate management—to strengthen the effectiveness of monetary policy. Given the asymmetric effects observed, monetary easing may be more effective in stimulating private sector credit than aggressive tightening in restraining it. Furthermore, improved coordination between monetary and fiscal authorities is necessary to prevent potential crowding-out effects and to create a stable environment that promotes sustainable credit growth and private sector development.

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